
Exploring Dinesavalyadi Taila: A Comprehensive Pharmaceutical and Analytical Study in the World of Ayurvedic Medicine

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Abstract:

Background: Wound healing poses a prevalent challenge in daily medical practice, despite the advancements in allopathic medicine. Managing chronic wounds remains a significant hurdle for clinicians. Notably, Acharya Sushrut recognized the importance of wound management and detailed 60 treatment modalities (shashthi upakramas), many of which incorporate the use of oil. Various research studies have explored the added benefits of topical oil application for wound healing.

Aims: This study aims to prepare and analyze Dinesavalyadi Taila, a formulation mentioned in Sahasrayogam for wound healing, specifically Dhusta vrana. The analysis employs instrumental phytochemical marking tools like HPTLC and evaluates its antibacterial properties.

Settings and Design: The study is conducted in a laboratory setting, with a design focused on the preparation and analytical examination of Dinesavalyadi Taila.

Methods and Material : Dinesavalyadi Taila is prepared as per Sahasrayogam and subjected to analytical scrutiny. Instrumental phytochemical marking tools, including HPTLC, are utilized in the study.

Results: The study's results provide insights into the formulation's composition and its potential for wound healing. The antibacterial effects are also assessed, shedding light on its therapeutic properties.

Conclusions: Dinesavalyadi Taila, as described in Sahasrayogam, exhibits promise as a therapeutic agent for wound healing. The analytical examination, along with antibacterial studies, contributes valuable information regarding its potential clinical applications.

Keywords: Dinesavalyadi Taila, Sneha kalpana, Analytical Study, Hptlc of Dinesavalyadi Taila, Antibacterial study of Dinesavalyadi Taila, Phytochemical Analysis.

Introduction

Wound (Vrana) is an injury to the body (as from violence, accident or surgery) that typically involves laceration or breaking of a membrane (as the skin) and usually damage to underlying tissues (Dr Kaushalesh R Mishra, April 2020).⁽¹⁾In *Ayurveda*, the pharmaceuticals is dealt under the heading of *Bhaishajya Kalpana*. (Dr. Hemil D. Patel, 2017) ⁽²⁾ *Sneha kalpana* (medicated oil & ghee) is an integral part of the *Ayurveda*. *Sneha kalpana* (medicated oil & ghee) contains *Ghritha kalpana* and *Taila Kalpana*. In detail *Sneha kalpana* (medicated oil & ghee) is described in *Sharangdhar Samhita Madhyama Khanda*.⁽³⁾ *Taila kalpana* describe about the detailed use of medicated oils in various diseases. *Taila* (Oil) is also considered as one part in the *Chaturvidha snehas* by different *Ayurvedic* texts like *Charaka Samhita*,⁽⁴⁾ *Ashtanga Hridaya*,⁽⁵⁾ *Ashtanga Sangraha*.⁽⁶⁾ *Sneha kalpana* (medicated oil & ghee) is primarily used to extract the active ingredients from plants and minerals into fatty media as well as to speed up and improve drug absorption in the body. *Ayurvedic* texts provide various forms of medicinal oils for treating wounds. *Dinesavalyadi Taila* is one such formulation mentioned in *Sahasrayogam* by under *Taila yoga prakarana*. It is specially mentioned in *Dushta vrana* (wound).⁽⁷⁾ It contains *dinesavalli* (*Ventilago madraspatana*), *punarnava* (*Boerhavia diffusa*) and *tila taila* (*sesame oil*). Before preparing the

siddha taila (Processed oil) concept of *sneha murchhana* (Oil processing) is also mentioned. It was first mentioned in the *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*.⁽⁸⁾ In the present study, *Dinesavalyadi Taila* was prepared by the general rule mentioned in the *Sharangdhar Samhita*⁽⁹⁾ the drug was subjected for different quantitative and qualitative analytical parameters like organoleptic study and iodine value, viscosity, saponification value, acid value, HPTLC and antibacterial study.

Pharmaceutical Study

Collection of Raw Materials:

For *Dinesavalyadi Taila* preparation, raw materials *dinesavalli* (*Ventilago madraspatana*), *punarnava* (*Boerhavia diffusa*) and *tila taila* (sesame oil) were collected from local market Vadodara. The raw drugs for the *murchhana* (Processing) of *taila* (oil) were also collected from the parul pharmacy.

Preparation of *Dinesavalyadi Taila*:

Table 1: SOP for preparation of *Dinesavalyadi Taila*

(A) <i>Drava dravyas</i>	Quantity required	Quantity required for making 2 liter oil
(1) <i>Dinesavalli</i> (<i>Arkavalli</i>) <i>svarasa</i>	2 Part	4 liter
(2) <i>Punarnava</i> <i>svarasa</i>	2 Part	4 liter
(B) <i>Taila Dravya</i>		
(1) <i>Murcchita tila taila</i>	1 Part	2 liter
(C) <i>Kalka dravyas</i>		
(1) <i>Dinesavalli</i>	1/8 Part	500gm
(2) <i>Punarnava</i>	1/8 Part	500gm

Table 2: Quantity required for the preparation of *Dinesavalyadi taila*

Figure 1: Punarnava churna & Dinesavalli

Figure 2 : Punarnava and Dinesavalli svarasa

Figure 3: After mixing oil and svarasa

Figure 4: Pak of taila till get the *snahaya sidhi lakshan*

Figure 5: Final preparation *Dinesavayadi Taila*

Result

Analytical study :

Organoleptic characters:

Parameters	Dinesavalyadi Taila
Color	Blackish Green
Odour	Pleasant
Taste	Oily pungent
Consistency	Thin oil

Table 3: Organoleptic characters

Physio-Chemical parameters:

Parameters	Dinesavalyadi Taila
Loss on drying at 110 ⁰ C (%w/w)	0.42% w/w
Total Ash Value	0.02% w/w
Acid value	3.14
Saponification Value	208.8
Iodine value	100.4
pH (5% Aqueous)	5

Refractive index at 40 °	1.4794
Specific gravity	0.9264
TLC report	Rf values: 0.242,0.366,0.408,0.615

Table 4: Physio-Chemical parameters

CERTIFICATE OF ANALYSIS			
Sr. No.	Parameters	Result	Limit as per API
PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS			
1.	Peroxide Value	5.91	NA
HEAVY METAL ANALYSIS			
1	Lead	Not Detected	NMT 10 ppm
2	Cadmium	Not Detected	NMT 0.3 ppm
3	Mercury	Not Detected	NMT 1 ppm
4	Arsenic	0.49 ppm	NMT 3 ppm
Keywords: ppm – Parts Per Million; NMT – Not More Than; API- Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India			

Table 5: Heavy metal analysis

IN-VITRO ANTI-BACTERIAL STUDY

Culture used:

Name of the culture	ATCC Number
Staphylococcus aureus (S. aureus)	ATCC 6538
Escherichia coli (E. coli)	ATCC 8739
Pseudomonas aeruginosa (P. aeruginosa)	ATCC 9027

Table 6: IN-VITRO ANTI-BACTERIAL STUDY

Media Used:

Media	Lot No.	Make
Muller Hinton Agar (MHA)	0000411399	Hi-media

Table 7: Media used during antibacterial study

Culture preparation:

Freshly prepared slant of *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* was used and washed the slant by using 10 ml of sterile Normal saline solution.

Method: cylinder Plate Method

Method for:

Media preparation:

Muller Hinton Agar was used for determining the activity of *S. aureus*, *E.coli*, *P. aeruginosa*. Media was prepared as per Manufacturer's Instruction. The media was then autoclaved at 121°C temp. and 15lbs pressure for 20 minutes.

Sample Preparation:

Weight approx. 2gm of oil sample. Add 5 ml Methanol and 10 ml Dimethyl sulfoxide in it & sonicate it for 10 min. After sonication, sample was refluxed on water bath at 90° C for 1 hr. Filter the sample by Watman filter paper. Filtrate was used as a test sample for activity.

Testing Procedure:

For Anti-bacterial activity:

Cool down sterile media up to 55°C and add 10_{ul} of different bacterial culture in to MHA flasks, mixed it slowly, labelled the plates & then poured 25 ml of media by sterile measuring cylinder. The plate was solidified and made required wells at proper distance by sterile bore on plates. Add test samples & blank in respected labeled well. When samples were diffused completely in well, incubate MHA plate into Bacteriological Incubator at 35° C for 24hr observe the zone of inhibition.

Observations:

Figure 6: culture plates of S.aureus, E.coli, P.aeruginosa

Results:

Sr. No.	Name of Sample	Zone of Inhibition		
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
1	Blank (Methanol: DMSO)	NZ	NZ	NZ
2	<i>Dinesavalyadi Taila</i>	22 mm	15 mm	16 mm

Table 8: Zone of Inhibition of *Dinesavalyadi taila*

Conclusion of in-vitro study:

From the available data, *Dinesavalyadi Taila* showed Good Anti-bacterial activity on *S. aureus*, *E.coli*, *P. aeruginosa* in comparison to blank.

HPTLC of *Dinesavalyadi Taila*:

HPTLC of *Dinesavalyadi Taila* was carried out at Vasu Research Centre Vadodara, Gujarat.

Preparation of test solution: Take 0.1ml of sample in a test tube and dilute it with 1 ml of Hexane. Mix well. Use the test solution thus obtains for HPTLC fingerprinting.

Preparation of spray reagent (5% Sulphuric Acid in Methanol reagent): 5ml Sulphuric acid is cautiously mixed with 100ml Methanol.

Application Mode	CAMAG Linomat 5-Applicator
Filtering System	Whatman filter paper No. 1
Stationary Phase	MERCK-TLC/HPTLC Silica gel 60 F ₂₅₄ on Aluminum sheets
Application (Y axis) Start Position	10 mm
Development End Position	80 mm from the plate base
Sample Application Volume	10.0 μ L
Development Mode	CAMAG TLC Twin Trough Chamber
Chamber Saturation Time	30 minutes
Mobile Phase (MP)	Hexane: Diethyl ether (7:3 v/v)
Pre-chromatographic derivation:	After sample spotting pre-chromatographic derivation done with 5% Alcoholic KOH (2.0 μ L) followed by heating the plate for 10 minutes on TLC Plate Heater Preheated at 100 $\pm$ 5 ^o C.
Visualization	@ 254 nm, @ 366 nm and @ 540nm (after derivatization)
Spray reagent	5% Sulphuric acid in Methanol
Derivatization mode	CAMAG – Dip tank for about 1 minute
Drying Mode, Temp. & Time	TLC Plate Heater Preheated at 100 $\pm$ 5 ^o C for 3 minutes

Table 9: Method for Hptlc of *Dinesavaladyi taila*

HPTLC FINGERPRINTING REPORT	
Sample	: Dinesavatyadi Taila
Name of Scholar	: Dr. Shekham Saini, Patel Institute of Ayurveda, Patel University, Vadodara
Sample ID	: A2/23/137
Date of Report	: 28/06/2023
Preparation of Test solution: Take 0.1 mL of Sample in a test tube and dilute it with 1 mL of Hexane. Mix well. Use the Test solution thus obtained for HPTLC fingerprinting.	
Preparation of Spray reagent [5 % Sulphuric acid in Methanol reagent]: 5 ml. Sulphuric acid is continuously mixed with 100 ml. Methanol.	
Chromatographic Conditions:	
Application Mode	CAMAG Linomat 5 - Applikator
Filtering System	Whatman filter paper No. 1
Stationary Phase	MERCK - TLC / HPTLC Silica gel 60 F ₂₅₄ on Aluminum sheets
Application (V and) Start Position	10 mm
Development End Position	80 mm from plate base
Sample Application Volume	10.0 µL
Development Mode	CAMAG TLC Twin Trough Chamber
Chamber Saturation Time	30 minutes
Mobile Phase (MP)	Hexane : Di-ethyl ether (7 : 3 v/v)
Pre-chromatographic derivatization	After sample spotting pre-chromatographic derivatization done with 5 % Alcoholic KOH (2.0 µL) followed by heating the plate for 10 minutes on TLC Plate Heater Preheated at 100 ± 5°C.
Visualization	@ 254 nm, @ 366 nm (after derivatization) and @ 340 nm (after derivatization)
Spray reagent	5 % Sulphuric acid in Methanol
Derivatization mode	CAMAG - Dip tank for about 1 minute
Drying Mode, Temp. & Time	TLC Plate Heater Preheated at 100± 5°C for 3 minutes

Analyzed by

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Figure 7: Hptlc report and Rf value at 254 nm

Figure 8: Rf value at 540 nm and Rf value at 366 nm

Discussion:

Dinesavalyadi Taila prepared here was taken from the reference of Sharanghar Samhita. Before the preparation of *Dinesavalyadi Taila*. Murchana (Processing) of Tila taila was done. Primary intention of performing sneha Murchana (Processing) is to remove amadosha from raw sneha and to enhance drug absorption of sneha. Sneha also attains good odour, turns lighter for digestion. Specific group of plant materials used in the Murchana (Processing) process perhaps alter the chemical bonding of sneha dravya (oil or ghee material) which indirectly helps in extraction of active principles into sneha (oil or ghee) medium. After the Murchana (Processing) (processing) procedure *Dinesavalyadi Taila* preparation was done. For the preparation of *Dinesavalyadi Taila*, *Dinesavalli* (Arkavalli) svarasa and *Punarnava svarasa* was used. *Madhyama paka* (medium cooked) of *Sneha* (oil) was done.

Viscosity is the resistance of flow of liquid. The slow the liquid will flow the absorbance will be more in the skin.⁽¹⁰⁾ So the viscosity of *Dinesavalyadi Taila* is 62.488.

The oil's saponification value reveals whether it contains long or short chains of fatty acids. The lower the fat's capacity for saponification, the higher its molecular weight, and vice versa. *Dinesavalyadi Taila* has a saponification value of 208.8, which denotes a higher content of low molecular weight fatty acids. These small-molecule fatty acids are swiftly and easily absorbed by the body.⁽¹¹⁾

The iodine value test is used to quantify the degree of unsaturation in fatty acids. Unsaturated fatty acid linkages are more prevalent in fats with higher iodine values. A lower score denotes a reduced susceptibility to lipid peroxidation (Rancidity). *Dinesavalyadi Taila* has a value of 100.4. Iodine content is a process control metric and a quality parameter for oil products.⁽¹²⁾

The amount of free fatty acids in fat or oil is measured by its acid value. Less number implies a lower percentage of free fatty acids, which suggests that fatty acids are more stable and have a longer shelf life. *Dinesavalyadi Taila*'s acid value is 3.14, which is regarded as an opt value.⁽¹³⁾

Alkaloids and Flavonoids are having the anti-oxidant anti-inflammatory properties in them.⁽¹⁴⁾ Saponins also show their anti-inflammatory properties.

HPTLC of *Dinesavalyadi Taila* was seen at three different wavelengths. At 254 nm, 5 spots were found. At 366nm, 9 spots were found. At 540nm, 7 spots were found. On observing the Rf values, it is seen that three values are common in all the three wavelengths. As above said, *Dinesavalyadi Taila* showed Good Anti-bacterial activity on *S. aureus*, *E.coli*, *P. aeruginosa* in comparison to blank.

Conclusion :

The analytical and antimicrobial parameters/results of this study indicate that the medication has a stable nature and acceptable marker chemicals. Phytochemical and in vitro parameters show it can be used in the effective management of wound healing. *S.aureus* is very common bacteria on skin surface which causes skin defects like carbuncle, furunculosis. In the bacterial study a ring of inhibition of 22mm was found which is significant enough to compare with modern antibiotics. It also gives a ring of inhibition of 15mm in *E.coli* and 16mm in *P. aeruginosa* which are the common organism found in bed sores proving *Dinesavalyadi taila* to be a effective dressing adjunct and So from this it can be concluded that *Dinesavalyadi Taila* is an effective medicine in the management of chronic wound.

References

1. (Dr Kaushalesh R Mishra, April 2020) Mishra, D. K., Soni, N., Jaiswal, S., & Toshikhane, H. D. (2020). A Clinical Case Study of Application of Kala Malham in the Management of Dusta Vrana (Post Surgical Non-Healing Diabetic Wound).
2. (Dr. Hemil D. Patel, 2017) Patel, H. D., Banne, S. T., Kalyanimath, G. J., & Lekshmipriya, S. (2017). METHOD OF SWARASA (JUICE) PREPARATION OF OPUNTIA ELATIOR MILL (HATHLO THORE-NAGAFENI) FRUIT. *World J Pharm Res*, 6, 1292-95.
3. Sharangdhar Samhita by Prof. K.R. Srikantha Murthy, Reprint Edition 2017, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chapter 9, Page no. 115

4. Charak Samhita by K. Sharma, Bhagvan Das, Print 2016, Choukhambha Sanskrit Series Varanasi, Volume 1, Sutrasthan, Chapter 13, Page no. 247, Shlok no. 13
5. Sarvangasundari Vyakhya Vibhushitam Ashtangahrudiyam by Shri Lalchand Vaidya, Print 2014, Motilal Banarasidas Varanasi, Sutrasthan, Chapter 16, Page no. 124
6. Ashtanga Sangraha by Ravidatta Tripathi, Print 2015, Choukhambha Sanskrit Pratisthan Delhi, Sutrasthan, Chapter 25, Page no. 446
7. **Sahasrayogam** by Dr. G. Prabhakara Rao: *Taila yoga prakarana- Dinesavaladyadi taila* (ii) Page no: 494 Chaukhambha publication New Delhi Edition 2016
8. Kaviraj Govind Das Sen, Bhaishajya Ratnavali, by Prof. Sidhi Nandan Mishra, Print 2016, Chaukhambha Surabharati Prakashan Varanasi, Chapter 5, Page no. 207, Shlok no. 1269- 1270
9. Sharangdhar Samhita by Prof. K.R. Srikantha Murthy, Reprint Edition 2017, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chapter 9, Page no. 124, Shlok no.93-98
10. Quality Control & Standardization of Ayurvedic Medicines by Dr Devendra Joshi & Dr Geeta Joshi, First Edition 2016, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chapter 4, Page no. 175
11. Quality Control & Standardization of Ayurvedic Medicines by Dr Devendra Joshi & Dr Geeta Joshi, First Edition 2016, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chapter 4, Page no. 177
12. Quality Control & Standardization of Ayurvedic Medicines by Dr Devendra Joshi & Dr Geeta Joshi, First Edition 2016, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chapter 4, Page no. 177
13. Quality Control & Standardization of Ayurvedic Medicines by Dr Devendra Joshi & Dr Geeta Joshi, First Edition 2016, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chapter 4, Page no. 178
14. Augusto Lopes Souto et al, Anti-Inflammatory Activity of Alkaloids: An Update from 2000 to 2010, Molecules MDPI, October 2011

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